

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

SPOCK2

(SPARC (osteonectin), cwcv and kazal like domains proteoglycan 2)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

Gene ID / UniProt ID / EC	9806 / Q92563
Target Nominator	TREAT-AD, AMP-AD
TREAT-AD Authors	Jesse Wiley ¹ , Greg Cary ² , Levon Halabelian ³ , and the Emory-Sage-SGC TREAT-AD Center
Therapeutic Area(s)	Alzheimer's disease
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Affiliations	¹ Sage Bionetworks, Seattle, WA, USA ² The Jackson Laboratory, Bar Harbor, ME, USA ³ The University of Toronto, Toronto, Canada

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Bioinformatic analysis: Target source & hypothesis

Protein constructs & expression methods: Baculovirus expression for structure determination

TARGET SOURCE & HYPOTHESIS

Why was the target selected? This target is found within a TMT proteomics network module that was highly correlated with cognition. This module (Module 42) contains several novel AD targets, including SMOC1 and SFRP1.

TREAT-AD Target Risk Score: 2.85 (rank #5982, 76.0th percentile)

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics and genetics evidence. The Target Risk Score represents the gene target's general relevance to Alzheimer's Disease, and is the sum of

the target's Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Target Risk Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being evidence of the strongest association with AD. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate these scores is available [here](#). This score was taken from Agora, Data Version syn13363290-v62.

The TREAT-AD Target Risk Score for this target is 2.85 out of 5 (rank #5982, 76.0th percentile). The individual score components include 0.98 of 3 for genetics, and 1.86 out of 2 for genomics. The meta-analysis of proteomic and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of SPOCK2 protein is significantly increased in brains from patients with AD.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (biodomains). These biological domains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biological domains via GO term annotations. SPOCK2 is

annotated to GO terms from the Structural Stabilization, Synapse, Metal Binding and Homeostasis, and Immune Response biological domains.

Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell expression data from the Seattle Alzheimer's Disease Brain Cell Atlas (SEA-AD). The distribution of expression values for all genes found in each broad cell type are displayed as violins. The expression of the target in subtypes within each broad class is shown as a point. Blue points show the summary expression of cells from individuals with no dementia, while red points show summary metrics of cells from dementia patients. Open circles reflect low confidence measures of expression. The expression of SPOCK2 is confidently detected in endothelial cells, as well as both inhibitory and excitatory neuron subtypes within this dataset.

Overall	rank	pctl	GeneticsScore	OmicsScore
2.846	5982	76.04	0.9835	1.862

SUMMARY OF PROJECT

This project follows from the discovery of SPOCK2 within an AD associated module that dovetails with previous work suggesting a role for this protein family in neuritic outgrowth and viability (see below for details and citations). There is very little known about the role of SPOCK2 in AD pathological progression or clinical dementia. We are developing the current target enabling package (TEP) to facilitate the future study of this gene and its role in neurodegeneration. The basic TEP will include identification of viable antibodies that are specific to this protein, the development of purified protein, and the bioinformatic characterization of SPOCK2 provided in the preceding section of this report. We hope this will stimulate

new investigations and lower the barrier to entry for future exploration of SPOCK2's role in AD pathogenesis.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

The SPOCK2 gene codes for the 424 amino acid Testican-2(TICN-2) protein containing a number of domains, including Kazal-like domains, EF hand extracellular calcium binding domains and a thyroglobulin domain(1) (UniProt: Q92563). SPOCK2 is expressed predominantly within the central nervous system within multiple neuronal subtypes in the hippocampus, cortex and olfactory bulb(1, 2). SPOCK2 is a heparin proteoglycan family member involved in the regulation of neurite outgrowth in brain suggestive of a role in brain development and cortical wiring(3, 4), potentially through the regulation of membrane-type matrix metalloproteinases (MT-MMPs)(3). SPOCK2 is downregulated in astrocyte tumors, and was identified as a member of a set of genes that appear to decrease astrocytoma and vascular smooth muscle growth(5). The developmental role in synapse formation and neuritic outgrowth regulation may be mediated through SPOCK2's association with members of the classical complement cascade (such as C1q) that are known regulators of glial synaptic elimination(6). There are multiple SPOCK family members that have differential expression timing and spatial restrictions during development, with SPOCK1 and SPOCK 2 being ubiquitously expressed in the adult mouse brain. Other members of the SPOCK family are expressed in a more restricted developmental stage, and disruption of their function leads to neuronal connectivity anomalies including changes in the density, size and myelination of the corpus callosum(7). These data support the general idea that SPOCK family members are important for neuronal development and given SPOCK2's high level expression across brain regions in the adult, may indicate a role in neuronal connectivity maintenance as well. Consistent with the speculative role of SPOCK family members in regulating vascular physiology, mouse models targeting Wnt/Beta-Catenin signaling impact a core set of genes, of which SPOCK2 is included, that are elements of the extracellular matrix, and are involved in the regulation of the vascular maturity of the blood-brain barrier(8). Potentially related to SPOCK2's role in brain development and regulation of cellular migration and development, breast cancer cells that express high levels of SPOCK2 metastasize into the brain with particular pathogenicity(9).

Little is known about the specific and unique function of SPOCK2 in brain function, and there are no published works linking SPOCK2 to Alzheimer's disease or neurodegeneration beyond the identification of SPOCK2 as a component of an enriched AD brain proteomic module(10). The identified proteomic module, known as module 42 (M42), consists of just 32 proteins, including SPOCK2, and which are linked with the highest observed levels of both pathological progression and cognitive decline measures within the study(10). The role of SPOCK2, or many members of M42, in neurodegeneration are unclear, but M42 does include APP, APOE, and LRP1 among its constituents, further supporting a strong role for this module in AD progression. The biological mechanism associating SPOCK2 with the role of other M42 proteins is not known but given the regulation of metalloproteinase function by SPOCK family members, and the direct cleavage of proteins such as APP by members of the metalloproteinase family, the role of SPOCK2 warrants further investigation. We hope that the resources we develop as part of this project will facilitate exploration of the biological role of SPOCK2 in AD pathogenesis.

RESULTS – THE TEP

Proteins Purified

SPOCK2_22-424_AviN_HisC: Baculovirus expression for structure determination. See **Additional Information** for experimental information on purification.

CONCLUSION

The tools presented here provide a foundation for further biological investigation of the role of SPOCK2 in AD.

FUNDING INFORMATION

The work performed by the Emory-Sage-SGC TREAT-AD Center has been funded by the National Institute on Aging through grant U54 AG065187.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Materials and Methods

Proteins Expression and Purification

All relevant plasmids are available on addgene: [TREAT-AD plasmid collection](#)

Gene name	SPOCK2
Uniprot ID	Q92563
Region	22-424

Description	May participate in diverse steps of neurogenesis. Binds calcium.
Synonyms	Testican-2
Construct ID	SPOCK2_22-424_AviN_HisC PBC040F02
Parental Vector	pFHMSP-AviN-LIC-C
Tag (N-terminal)	MKFLVNVALVFMVVYISYIYAAAGSAGLNDIFEAQKIEWHEGSAGGSG
Tag (C-terminal)	EFVEHHHHHHHH
Protein mass (with tag)	51257.85 Da
Extinction Coefficient with tag (M⁻¹ cm⁻¹)	79880
Protein sequence (with tag)	MKFLVNVALVFMVVYISYIYAAAGSAGLNDIFEAQKIEWHEGSAGGSGAEGDAKGLK EGETPGNFMEDEQWLSSISQYSGKIKHWNRFDEVEDDYIKSWEDNQQGDEALDT TKDPCQKVKCSRHKVCIAQGYQRAMCISRKKLEHRIKQPTVKLHGNKDSICKPCH MAQLASVCGSDGHTYSSVCKLEQQACLSSKQLAVRCEGPCPCPTEQAATSTADGK PETCTGQDLADLGDRLRDWFQLLHENSQNGSASSVAGPASGLDKSLGASCKDSI GWMFSKLDTSADLFLDQTELAAILNDKYEVCIRPFNFSCDTYKDGRVSTAEWFCFC FWREKPPCLAELERIQIQEAAKKPGIFIPSCDEDEGYRKMQCDQSSGDCWCVDQ LGLELTGTRTHGSPDCDDIVGFGSDFGSGVGEDEEEKETEEAGEEAEDEEAGEAG EADDGGYIW FVEHHHHHHHH

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Purified Protein	
IMAC, Ni (step 1): SPOCK2_22-424_AviN_HisC	
SEC (step 2): SPOCK2_22-424_AviN_HisC	
Intact Mass Deconvolution:	N/A
Observed Mass:	N/A
Protein yield:	3.7 mg/L of culture

Expression and Purification Protocol	
Expression host	Insect cells: Sf9 (<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>)
Expression Medium	I-Max Insect Media W/ L-Glutamine, Wisent Biocentre
Transformation and storage	The baculovirus expression vector system (BEVS), specifically Bac-to-Bac Expression System (Invitrogen), employing <i>Autographa californica</i> multiple nucleopolyhedrovirus (AcMNPV) has been used for expression screening and production of target protein. The plasmid transfer vector containing the gene of interest was transformed into DH10Bac E. coli competent cells to generate recombinant viral bacmid DNA. Adherent Sf9 cells were then transfected with bacmid DNA to generate recombinant viruses used for the baculovirus-mediated production in the insect cells.
Expression	For the scale-up productions, suspension cultures of the baculovirus-infected insect cells, (SCBIC) were prepared by infection of the Sf9 cells with the corresponding P2 viruses. On the day of production, 2 L of Sf9 cells (cell viability > 97%) in 2.5 L Tunair shake flasks or 4 L in 5 L reagent bottles were diluted to a cell density of 4×10^6 /mL. These cells were infected directly with 10-12 mL/L of suspension culture of baculovirus-infected insect cells and incubated at a lowered temperature of 25 °C, at 145 rpm. Infected cells' density and viability along with the cell sizes monitored after 72 hours post-infection time to be able to collect

	cells for purification at the optimal conditions when Sf9 cells are well infected, usually in 5-6 days after the post-infection time.
Purification buffers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lysis buffer: 50 mM Tris (pH 8.0), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 2. Wash Buffer: 50 mM Tris (pH 8.0), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 5 mM imidazole 3. Elution Buffer (EB): 50 mM Tris (pH 8.0), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 250 mM imidazole 4. SEC buffer: 20 mM HEPES (pH 7.4), 300 mM NaCl, 2mM TCEP 5. IEC buffer: 20 mM HEPES (pH 7.4), 260 mM NaCl, 2mM TCEP 6. TALON beads, equilibrated in Lysis buffer.
Purification step 1: IMAC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Spin down cells @6500RPM for 15min 2. Transfer each 1.5L supernatant to a 2.8L flask with 150ml 10X PBS. 3. Add (2ml/L) Ni-sepharose beads to the supernatant and shake at 100RPM at 18 °C for 60 min. 4. Transfer the supernatant + beads to an open column to collect the beads and keep the flowthrough. 5. Wash beads with 50CV of lysis buffer. 6. Wash column with 1CV of wash buffer. 7. Elute protein with 5CV elution buffer. Analyse the EB fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using the Bradford assay. 8. Add beads (2ml /L) to the collected flowthrough for second binding same condition and repeat the same wash and elution after 1hour shaking.
Purification step 2: Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Purify the protein further by Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC) on a HiLoad Superdex S200 26/60 column in SEC buffer at 3 ml/min. 2. Analyze fractions by SDS-PAGE. Pool fractions containing protein of desired purity for next step.

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